

Antimicrobial Agents—Part III[†]: Synthesis and Antimicrobial Activity of Some New Aryloxyalkyl Esters of 3-Allyl/methyl/chloro-4-Hydroxybenzoic Acids

D. R. SHRIDHAR* and C. V. REDDY SASTRY

Research & Development Department, Indian Drugs & Pharmaceuticals Limited, Hyderabad-500 087

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3-Allyl/methyl/chloro-4-hydroxybenzoic acids have been condensed with different aryloxyalkyl bromides to give the corresponding esters. These esters were screened for their *in-vitro* antibacterial, antimycobacterial and antifungal properties against a variety of bacteria and fungi.

THE synthesis and antimicrobial activity of some aryloxyalkyl esters of *p*-hydroxybenzoic acid have been described earlier¹. In continuation of this work we report here the preparation of some new aryloxyalkyl esters of 4-hydroxybenzoic acid having allyl, methyl or chloro group adjacent to the hydroxy function with a view to study the effect of these three substituents and compare the results with those of *p*-hydroxybenzoic acid esters.

This paper describes the synthesis of aryloxyalkyl esters of 3-allyl/methyl/chloro-4-hydroxybenzoic acids (type I) which were obtained by condensing

the respective 4-hydroxybenzoic acids with appropriate aryloxyalkyl bromide² in DMF in the presence of sodium bicarbonate following the method of Parker³. The purity and homogeneity of all the compounds were checked by TLC and characterisation done by IR and elemental analyses.

All the esters thus prepared were subjected to *in vitro* antibacterial and antimycobacterial screening by serial dilution tube method and antifungal testing by agar dilution assay method as described earlier¹.

Experimental

Melting points were determined in closed glass capillaries using a sulfuric acid bath and are uncorrected. IR spectra were recorded in nujol

with Perkin-Elmer-237 grating IR spectrometer and elemental analyses were performed in the micro-analytical laboratory of this department using Hosli micro-combustion apparatus MK 101.

3-Allyl⁴-, 3-methyl⁵ and 3-chloro⁶-4-hydroxybenzoic acids were prepared according to the known methods.

Synthesis of β -phenoxyethyl-(3-allyl-4-hydroxy) benzoate (1, Table I)

A mixture of 3-allyl-4-hydroxybenzoic acid (1.78 g, 0.01 mol), β -phenoxyethyl bromide (2.01 g, 0.01 mol) and sodium bicarbonate (0.85 g, 0.01 mol) in freshly distilled DMF (15 ml) was heated in an oil bath at 130-140° for 6 hr. The cooled reaction mixture was poured into ice-water, made basic by adding sodium bicarbonate solution and the resulting solid was filtered. The dried solid was recrystallised from benzene-Pet. ether (40-60°) to give the title compound as colourless shining needles, $\nu_{\text{max}}^{\text{nujol}}$ 3350 cm⁻¹ (OH) and 1700 cm⁻¹ (ester C=O).

All the compounds reported in Table 1 were prepared in a similar manner.

Results and Discussion

On comparing the screening results reported in Table 2 with those obtained earlier¹, it is clear that the introduction of allyl, methyl or a chloro group adjacent to the hydroxy function in the benzoic acid moiety of these esters results in the slight enhancement of their *in vitro* antibacterial activity against *S. aureus*, *S. faecalis*, *K. pneumoniae*, *Ps. aeruginosa* and *A. tumefaciens* with a few exceptions. Furthermore, five esters of 3-allyl-4-hydroxybenzoic acid (compound nos. 1 and 3-6) have exhibited appre-

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TABLE 1—ARYLOXYALKYL ESTERS OF 3-ALLYL/METHYL/CHLORO-4-HYDROXYBENZOIC ACIDS (I)

Comp. No.	R	R ₁	n	M.P. °C	Yield %	Molecular Formula	% of Carbon		% of Hydrogen	
							Found	Calc.	Found	Calc.
1	CH ₂ CH=CH ₂	H	2	100-102	55	C ₁₈ H ₁₈ O ₄	72.19	72.49	6.04	6.04
2	CH ₃ CH=CH ₂	2-Cl	2	85-87	85	C ₁₈ H ₁₇ ClO ₄	65.22	64.98	5.56	5.11
3	CH ₂ CH=CH ₂	H	3	94-96	58	C ₁₉ H ₂₀ O ₄	73.00	73.07	6.35	6.40
4	CH ₂ CH=CH ₂	2-Cl	3	87-89	43	C ₁₉ H ₁₉ ClO ₄	65.45	65.80	5.47	5.48
5	CH ₂ CH=CH ₂	3-CH ₃	3	Liquid (b _p 250°)	55	C ₂₀ H ₂₂ O ₄	73.07	73.62	6.65	6.75
6	CH ₂ CH=CH ₂	H	4	69-70	37	C ₂₀ H ₂₂ O ₄	73.91	73.62	6.75	6.75
7	CH ₃ CH=CH ₂	2-Cl	4	75-76	45	C ₂₀ H ₂₁ ClO ₄	66.73	66.58	6.30	5.82
8	CH ₂ CH=CH ₂	3-CH ₃ , 6-Cl	4	89-91	71	C ₂₁ H ₂₃ ClO ₄	67.51	67.28	6.62	6.14
9	CH ₂ CH=CH ₂	2-Cl	5	70-71	46	C ₂₁ H ₂₃ ClO ₄	66.73	67.28	6.45	6.14
10	CH ₃	H	2	100-102	85	C ₁₆ H ₁₆ O ₄	70.23	70.58	6.06	5.88
11	CH ₃	2-Cl	2	110-112	76	C ₁₆ H ₁₅ ClO ₄	62.29	62.65	5.30	4.89
12	CH ₃	H	3	97-99	71	C ₁₇ H ₁₈ O ₄	71.81	71.32	6.31	6.29
13	CH ₃	2-Cl	3	95-97	31	C ₁₇ H ₁₇ ClO ₄	63.07	63.65	5.55	5.30
14	CH ₃	H	4	100-102	80	C ₁₈ H ₂₀ O ₄	71.77	72.00	6.85	6.66
15	CH ₃	2-Cl	4	124-126	82	C ₁₈ H ₁₉ ClO ₄	64.57	64.60	5.88	5.63
16	Cl	H	2	96-97	69	C ₁₅ H ₁₅ ClO ₄	61.12	61.55	4.80	4.44
17	Cl	2-Cl	2	101-103	31	C ₁₅ H ₁₄ Cl ₂ O ₄	55.41	55.05	3.46	3.67
18	Cl	2-Cl	3	123-125	80	C ₁₆ H ₁₄ Cl ₂ O ₄	56.58	56.30	4.21	4.10
19	Cl	2-Cl	4	111-113	54	C ₁₇ H ₁₆ Cl ₂ O ₄	58.00	57.46	4.88	4.50
20	Cl	3-CH ₃ , 6-Cl	4	85-87	43	C ₁₈ H ₁₈ Cl ₂ O ₄	58.89	58.55	5.50	4.88
21	Cl	2-Cl	5	94-96	48	C ₁₈ H ₁₈ Cl ₂ O ₄	58.37	58.55	5.23	4.88

TABLE 2—ANTIBACTERIAL AND ANTIFUNGAL ACTIVITIES, MIC (µg/ml)*

(i) Comp. No.	BACTERIA†					
	<i>S. aureus</i>	<i>S. faecalis</i>	<i>K. pneumoniae</i>	<i>Ps. aeruginosa</i>	<i>A. tumefaciens</i>	<i>M. tuberculosis</i> H ₃₇ RV
1	>200	>200	>200	25	>200	10
2	>200	>200	>200	10	>200	>200
3	25	25	25	10	25	25
4	25	25	25	10	>200	25
5	25	25	25	10	200	25
6	25	25	25	10	>200	10
7	>200	>200	>200	5	>200	>200
8	>200	50	>200	25	>200	>200
9	>200	25	200	10	>200	>200
10	>200	>200	>200	25	>200	>200
11	>200	>200	>200	>200	>200	>200
12	>200	>200	25	50	>200	>200
13	25	25	25	10	50	>200
14	25	25	25	10	25	>200
15	200	>200	>200	5	>200	>200
16	50	50	50	25	50	>200
17	25	25	10	5	10	>200
18	200	200	>200	100	100	>200
19	10	10	10	5	10	>200
20	10	10	10	5	25	>200
21	10	10	10	5	10	>200

(ii)	FUNGI**						
	<i>T. mentagrophytes</i>	<i>T. rubrum</i>	<i>M. canis</i>	<i>M. gypseum</i>	<i>Cr. neoformans</i>	<i>S. schenckii</i>	<i>H. capsulatum</i>
9	25	25	25	200	>200	>200	50
12	25	25	50	50	>200	50	50
13	100	100	25	200	>200	>200	>200
14	100	200	25	100	>200	>200	100
16	>200	>200	100	100	25	>200	25

* Minimum inhibitory concentration (MIC) was expressed in terms of micrograms per milliliter (µg/ml) at which the growth of the test organism was completely inhibited.

† All the compounds were also tested *in vitro* against *S. typhi*, *S. dysenteriae*, *V. cholerae*, *E. coli* and *P. vulgaris* but found to be inactive at test concentrations (200 µg/ml).

** All the compounds were also screened *in vitro* against *C. albicans*, *E. floccosum* and *A. fumigatus* but found to be inactive at test concentrations (200 µg/ml) and only the significant results are entered in the table.

ciable antituberculosis activity against *M. tuberculosis* H₃₇RV at 10-25 µg/ml whereas the 3-methyl and 3-chloro analogues are completely devoid of this activity as are the parent *p*-hydroxybenzoic acid esters¹.

3-chloro-4-hydroxybenzoic acid esters are relatively more active than the corresponding 3-allyl or 3-methyl analogues. Thus compound nos. 19-21 having a 3-chloro substituent have exhibited highest *in vitro* antibacterial activity against both gram +ve (*S. aureus* and *S. faecalis*) and gram -ve (*K. pneumoniae* and *Ps. aeruginosa*) bacteria at 5-10 µg/ml and are more active than the corresponding 3-allyl or 3-methyl derivatives. None of these esters is active against *E. coli*, *S. typhi*, *S. dysenteriae*, *V. cholerae* and *P. vulgaris* at test concentrations (200 µg/ml).

Five esters (compound nos. 9, 12-14 and 16) possess moderate *in vitro* antifungal activity against *T. rubrum*, *T. mentagrophytes*, *M. canis*, *M. gypseum*, *S. schenkii* and *H. capsulatum*. Of these, phenoxypropyl-(3-methyl-4-hydroxy) benzoate (compound no. 12) has the highest activity with MIC values at 25-50 µg/ml.

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